

CUMULATIVE PRESSURES AT SEA DEMAND ACTION: TOOLS TO MAKE MANAGEMENT POSSIBLE

How can this Policy Brief support you?

This Policy Brief shows the importance of cumulative pressures assessment (**CEA**) as the mechanisms of natural and anthropogenic change to the natural and societal marine environment. It explains why cumulative pressures from natural and human-induced change must be addressed in marine management. Practitioners increasingly have to manage activities and pressures in complex marine areas, and so this Policy Brief presents practical tools created by **GES4SEAS** to improve the knowledge-base in decision-making for comprehensive marine management. The tools link pressures and ecosystem components, visualise cumulative effects and integrate quantitative and qualitative information, even with limited data. They support policy-relevant applications to manage the causes and consequences of marine changes.

Key Messages

Cumulative pressures emanate from having many human activities occurring together in complex marine ecosystems.

Previously, managing these activities has been achieved by tackling them sectorally. This prevents a more high-level strategic perspective involving all human activities and their cumulative pressures.

There is an increasing need for determining synergistic and antagonistic pressure interactions.

GES4SEAS has developed conceptual, technical and/or web-based tools for understanding the effects of these cumulative pressures at sea and to enable informed management decisions.

Applying those tools provides insights as to where and why the increased risk of cumulative impacts might be expected.

The GES4SEAS toolbox combines custom-made tools to explore further impacts of specific pressures to prioritise targeted management measures.

GES4SEAS has improved the usability of existing approaches and integrated them into tools that support all stages of CEA.

Narrative of the problem, with GES4SEAS examples

Cumulative pressures are defined as aggregated, collective and accruing ecosystem changes created by a combination of human activities and natural processes. They can interact antagonistically and/or synergistically and additive.

Managing cumulative pressures in complex marine ecosystems requires determining the activity-, pressures- and natural and social system effects-footprints and the links between these. This requires understanding that the human activities are managed ultimately to control the pressures and effects on the natural and human systems. It is then necessary to determine the increase in spatial and temporal scales with a progression from activity to pressure to effect. Marine management and governance aim to control pressures and effects by licencing and/or permitting the activities.

Previous work has taken an additive approach to multiple pressures by merely listing the activities and assuming pressures emanate from these. However, this does not account for any weighting or double-counting of the pressures. Hence, there is the need for the newly developed and validated tools to be widely applied for CEA and linked to policy instruments. As such, **GES4SEAS** has built on previous work to create industry-standard tools within a comprehensive toolbox:

GES4SEAS has developed **Tikta**, an open-source software, with an analysis module containing methods to determine CEA spatially. This module also includes the updated **Nested Environmental status Assessment Tool (NEAT)** for use in the **Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD)** since it follows the MSFD assessment guidelines in a flexible way. This can be used in complex sea areas to implement the **Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP)** Directive, designate areas for conservation, support decisions on authorizing new activities at sea or managing existing ones and create Programmes of Measures for achieving GES against multiple pressures.

In the same way, determining and connecting the links between activities, pressures and effects can be facilitated using **Pressure2Eco**, developed by **GES4SEAS**. This enables data preparation for accurate incorporation into Tikta CEA, thereby reducing uncertainty in comprehensively representing the system.

Pressure2Eco summarizes a priori the assessment and displays the impact linkages from human activities (left) to pressures (middle) and then to the target ecosystem components (right); the example above illustrates a case for coastal fishes (MSFD D1) and benthic broad habitats (D6).

Similarly, the **GES4SEAS** tool SCAIRM, is a Spatially explicit Cumulative Impact Assessment method to guide Ecosystem-Based Management. It incorporates human activities, their pressures and their impacts on ecosystem components and services and societal goods and benefits. Its categorical Impact Risk-based method harmonises qualitative and quantitative information into a single system for use in both data-poor and data-rich situations. Its decision tree guides management while also allowing scenario testing (e.g. by decreasing the severity or extent of activities or effects).

Other issue-specific tools, developed by **GES4SEAS** and applied Europe-wide, address important topics, such as harmful blooms and invasive species, allowing their management amongst multiple pressures. CIMPAL (Cumulative IMPacts of invasive ALien species) has been expanded to combine these issues, show the impacts on ecosystem services and societal goods and benefits and facilitate decision-making, thereby designing adequate Programmes of Measures especially for MSFD descriptors, such as D2 (non-indigenous species) and D5 (eutrophication). Other issue-specific tools, developed by **GES4SEAS** and applied Europe-wide, address important topics, such as harmful blooms and invasive species, allowing their management amongst multiple pressures. CIMPAL (Cumulative IMPacts of invasive ALien species) has been expanded to combine these issues, show the impacts on ecosystem services and societal goods and benefits and facilitate decision-making, thereby designing adequate Programmes of Measures especially for MSFD descriptors, such as D2 (non-indigenous species) and D5 (eutrophication).

Policy implications

European Directives

- Marine Strategy Framework Directive reporting
- Natura 2000 Directives (Habitats, Wild Birds)
- Maritime Spatial Planning Directive
- Nature Restoration Regulation, in taking decisions European Environment Agency (Marine Messages)

Other Policy / International Objectives

- Regional Seas Conventions reporting
- UN Convention on Law of the Sea
- ICES

Sustainable Development Goals

The GES4SEAS tools link directly or indirectly to many of the SDG:

Beyond the State-of-the-Art

The **GES4SEAS** tools show that the project has gone well beyond the state-of-the-art, allowing managers to take informed decisions, track all sources of pressures and risk to ecosystem components in a comprehensive way and therefore design measures to reduce the effects of multiple pressures at sea. Prior to **GES4SEAS**, marine management had centred on tackling the pressures from activities on a case-by-case basis by licensing or merely allowing the activities.

Tikta allows managers to respond to the MSPD and MSFD, among others, in a structured way to take informed decisions. Pressure2eco builds on policy relevant requirements and in-depth explores the causal pathways between human activities, pressures and expected adverse effects on ecosystem components and functions. Furthermore, these are the first tools that enable a standardised mapping of human pressures for CEA. They harmonise major impact linkage frameworks in one platform, provide complete assessment diagnostics while helping planners, managers and researchers to map pressures consistently and reveal structural uncertainty.

Key Facts

Most seas worldwide, and especially in Europe, are subject to many overlapping activities and hence there are conflicts between these with the natural marine status.

Acknowledging and assessing cumulative pressures and their effects are key to informing decision-making in protecting our seas.

The suite of tools developed under GES4SEAS support national, EU, regional and global policies which aim to achieve a good and fit-for-purpose marine environmental status.

The effective use of the available tools requires both a good conceptual understanding of the marine natural and social system and also adequate and fit-for purpose quality-controlled and collated data.

Authors:

Elliott, M., Borja, A., Berg, T., Ortega, M., Coll, M., Cubillos, J., Piet, G., Papadopoulou, N., Rehren, J., Uyarra, M.C., Stelzenmüller, V. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19085187

References from GES4SEAS

For GES4SEAS resources and references click this [link](#) or scan this QR code

For references outside GES4SEAS see:

Elliott, M., et al., 2020. Mar. Poll. Bull., 155: 111201; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2020.111201>.

For additional resources from the GES4SEAS project, visit the webpages: <https://www.ges4seas.eu> and <https://www.ges4seas.eu/toolbox/>

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